

Diversity And Inclusion In The Workplace: Benefits, Challenges And Solutions

MURAGE JANE KARUANA

Research Scholar
Swiss School of Business and Management
Geneva, Switzerland

DR. R. V. PALANIVEL

Professor
Berlin School of Business and Innovation
Berlin, Germany

ABSTRACT

Diversity and Inclusion have become important ingredients for driving an organization's success. This is due to globalization, which has led to workplaces having more diverse employees from all cultures, genders, ages, ethnicities, religions, disabilities, and sexual orientations, among others. This article delves into the benefits of pursuing diversity and inclusion in the workplace, the challenges, and the solutions to overcome the challenges. A survey was also conducted on a road construction firm where data was collected using self-administered questionnaires to 120 employees. The study used descriptive statistics in the analysis of data. Data was presented in charts and tables. The survey found that 84% of the respondents admitted that diversity and inclusion is an important component in the workplace. The respondents also felt that diversity and inclusion in the workplace would reduce conflicts, improve customer service, improve creativity and innovation among employees, increase employee morale and productivity, and create opportunities for promotion. The research also found that some of the obstacles to diversity and inclusion in the workplace are discrimination, lack of diverse recruitment, limited resources, leadership commitment, and lack of training. Some of the strategies observed that would improve inclusivity are employee resource groups, inclusive training and development, leadership commitment, and open communication.

Key Words: Diversity, Inclusion, Belonging.

1.1 Introduction

Due to globalization, workplaces have become more diverse, with employees from all sorts of cultures, ethnicities, religions, gender, age, religion, disability, and sexual orientation, among others. This diversity offers a productive ground for rich ideas, which enables businesses to solve problems faster since there is a broader base of solutions to choose from. Therefore, this calls for policies to incorporate all these diversities within the organization to ensure that all employees feel a sense of belonging.

Diversity refers to the various attributes, backgrounds, and experiences that individuals bring within a workplace. On the other hand, inclusion refers to cultures and practices within the workplace that make individuals feel respected, valued, and fully incorporated within their workplace.

Integrating diverse ideas and inclusive practices contributes significantly to innovation, unique capabilities, and the performance of the company. Diversity and inclusion should not only identify the differences but should create an environment where every individual is valued and respected and therefore, feels a sense of belonging

Diversity and Inclusion are not merely complying with legal requirements; it is linked to innovation, company performance, and employee engagement.

Research has shown that diverse teams perform better than homogenous teams through creativity and novel skills. Inclusive workplaces bring a sense of belonging which leads to better productivity, job satisfaction, and retention of employees.

Diversity and Inclusion cannot be overemphasized. It contributes to a workforce that has various experiences and perspectives which leads to innovative ways and approaches to solving various problems. A workplace that incorporates diversity can ensure fairness, thereby creating an environment where people feel supported and valued.

Human capital is the most important factor of production since it is the one that operates all the other factors. For an organization to thrive it needs to have the right people with the expertise professionally, academically, and socially. This means that there will be individuals from diverse backgrounds and therefore, inclusion is key in incorporating each of these individuals.

The paper will, therefore, delve into the benefits of diversity and inclusion in the workplace, the challenges, and how to overcome them. Research will be conducted in a road construction firm, the findings will help support the topic of this article.

1.2 Statement of the Problem

Diversity and Inclusion in the workplace has gained a lot of attention globally. Many countries have established laws, policies, and practices to conform to this new change.

In Kenya for example there is the new constitution 2010 and various

Acts of Parliament which discourages all forms of discrimination and incorporates diversity and inclusion.

Despite all these, some have just remained as laws but have not been implemented. Therefore, this study sought to investigate how far diversity and inclusivity have been incorporated in the workplace.

1.3 Specific Objectives

To investigate employees' perception of workplace diversity and inclusion in a road construction firm.

1.4 Research Questions

What is the employees' perception of workplace diversity and inclusion in a road construction firm?

2 Literature Review

This section incorporates theories that support diversity and inclusion through the theoretical reviews, the delves into previous work of scholars in the empirical review.

2.1 Theoretical Review

This section delves into the theories that support diversity and inclusion, it will look at the Social Identity and Categorization theory and the Optimal Distinctiveness theory.

2.1.1 Social Identity and Categorization Theory

Social Identity theory recognizes the human desire to be part of a social group and the habit of comparing one social group with another. The theory identifies that people will do anything possible to maintain a positive social identity. This leads to biases, discrimination, gender differences, and racial conflict.

Social Categorization theory, on the other hand, explains the natural way by which people identify themselves against others by forming distinct social groups. This occurs when a person starts thinking of male versus female, young versus old, black versus white.

This is why a workplace should incorporate the various diverse employees and bring them together so that there can be harmony and everyone feels included and a sense of belonging.

2.1.2 Optimal Distinctiveness Theory

Optimal Distinctiveness Theory says that social identities are a result of the need for inclusion and distinctiveness. . There is a conflict between balancing being a part of a group and maintaining individuality. Inclusion is the need to connect with others, a desire to belong and feel wanted within a social group. People usually change their behaviors and identities to fit into groups that they wish to be a part of.

This is why in a workplace employee service groups should be available so that employees can join them instead of allowing them to form their own which may be biased or discriminatory.

2.2 Empirical Review

This section looks at what other scholars have found out on the benefits, challenges, and solutions on the topic of diversity and inclusion in the workplace.

in their work titled *Managing Workforce Diversity and Inclusion: A Critical Review and Future Directions* indicated the benefits of diversity and inclusion in the workplace as a marketing strategy, it is also used as resource acquisition, brings better problem-

solving skills and also brings about creativity and innovation. The work also identified solutions to incorporate diversity and inclusion in the workplace as diverse recruitment and hiring practices, inclusive training and development, establishment of employee resource groups and programs that help employees manage work-life balance.

in his work titled *Diversity, Equity, and Inclusion in the Workplace: Strategies for Achieving and Sustaining a Diverse Workforce* observed the benefits of diversity and inclusion as a better understanding of the customer, more creativity, and innovation, it aids in recruiting and preserving top talent and provides a positive workplace culture. The challenges he observed are unconscious biases, lack of diversity at the top, resistance to change, and lack of accountability. The following were the solutions given: holding leadership accountable, diverse recruitment and hiring practices, developing a diverse talent pipeline, creating an inclusive workplace culture, and measuring and monitoring progress.

In *Effects of Age and Culture Diversity on the Performance of Quality Control Organizations in Nairobi County-Kenya* observed the benefits of diversity and inclusion as more creativity and innovation and it aids in recruiting and preserving top talent. They observed leadership commitment and inclusive training and development as ways to improve diversity and inclusion in the workplace.

In *Influence of Human Resource Diversity Management Practices on performance of non-governmental Government Agencies in Kenya* found that the benefit of diversity and inclusion in the workplace is it brings about more creativity and innovation. The researcher found out that some of the solutions to the challenges faced in diversity and inclusion are leadership commitment,

developing a recruitment strategy that stresses the need for diversification, and inclusive training and development.

In *Diversity and Inclusion in the Workplace: Best practices for HR professionals*, the researcher noticed the challenges facing diversity and inclusion in the workplace as lack of inclusive leadership, resistance to change, inadequate resources, and limited commitment from top management. The researcher offered solutions such as leadership commitment, diverse recruitment, and hiring practices, inclusive training, and development, creating employee resource groups, and transparent policies and practices.

In *Managing Workplace Diversity: A Kenyan Perspective* identified the challenge of diversity and inclusion in the workplace as resistance to change. The researcher suggested the solutions as developing a recruitment strategy that stresses the need for diversification, inclusive training, and development, encouraging open communication and teamwork, and seeking periodic feedback from staff and management.

In *Workforce diversity management practices and employee performance among selected civil society organizations in Kenya* offered solutions to achieve diversity and inclusion as leadership commitment, inclusive training and development, transparent policies and practices, and manager accountability mechanisms.

In *Innovative Strategies for managing workforce diversity in Kenyan leading corporations in the present global scenario* came up with solutions for diversity and inclusion in the workplace which are leadership commitment and transparent policies and practices.

In an effort of workforce diversity management on the performance of international

development non-governmental organizations in Kenya identified the solutions to diversity and inclusion in the workplace as diverse recruitment and hiring practices, inclusive training and development, and encouraging open communication and teamwork.

From the research reviewed, it is evident that diversity and inclusion bring many benefits to organizations, which also come with various challenges, but there are possible solutions to these challenges. Therefore, all organizations should embrace diversity and inclusion in the workplace.

3. Research Methodology

Research has shown that diverse teams perform better than homogenous teams by bringing on board creativity and novel skills.

To examine this, a survey was carried out on a sample of 120 employees working in a road construction firm. Data was collected using self-administered questionnaires. The study used descriptive statistics in the analysis of data. Data was analyzed by using percentages with the results presented in graphs and tables.

4. Results and Interpretations

In this section, the results and the interpretations of the data are explained.

4.1 Demographics of the Respondents

The demographics of the respondents are presented in Table 1 below. The construction firm has 53% male and 47% female, this is a good balance considering that construction is believed to be male-dominated. From the age group, we have 75% of the employees more than 35 years old, some improvement is needed to have more young people for continuity purposes. In terms of education, everyone has a diploma and above, this is good. For experience, they are also doing well,

85% have experience of 5 years and above.

Table 1: Demographics of the respondents

Variable	Levels	Percentages
Gender	Male	53%
	Female	47%
Age Group	19-25	2%
	26-35	23%
	36-45	45%
	Over 45	30%
Education	Diploma	52%
	Bachelor	36%
	Master	7%
	Post Graduate	4%
	PHD	1%
Experience	Up to 1 year	2%
	2-4 years	15%
	5-10 years	48%
	Over 10 years	35%
Job Position	Employees	75%
	Supervisors	15%
	Management	10%

4.2 Importance of Diversity and Inclusion in an Organization

The majority of the respondents (84%) are aware of the importance of diversity in an organization. 40% of the respondents view diversity as very important, 44% as important, 8% were neutral and 8 % viewed it as not important. This shows that diversity and inclusion is a crucial component in an organization. This is represented in Figure 1 below

Figure 1: Importance of Diversity

4.3 The effect of more emphasis on diversity and inclusion

The respondents felt that if more emphasis was put on diversity and inclusion in the workplace then 92% felt conflicts would decrease, 75% felt customer service would improve, 92% felt creativity and innovation would improve, 88% felt employee morale and productivity would improve and 80% felt that opportunities for promotion would be created.

This emphasizes the need for diversity and inclusion in the workplace so that an organization can enjoy all these benefits.

This is presented in Figure 2 below.

Figure 2; Emphasis on Diversity

4.4 Obstacles to Diversity and Inclusion

The respondents felt the following were the main obstacles to diversity and inclusion in the workplace, Discrimination at 94%, lack of Diverse recruitment at 98%, limited resources at 97%, Leadership commitment at 93%, and lack of training at 91%.

This emphasizes the need for organizations to give priority to these issues so that they can be able to reap the benefits of diversity and inclusion in the workplace.

This is presented below in Figure 3.

Figure 3: Obstacles to Diversity and Inclusion

4.5 Strategies to improve inclusivity in the workplace

The respondents rated the following strategies to improve inclusivity, employee resource groups at 97%, Inclusive training, and development at 80%, leadership commitment at 88%, and open communication at 86%

There is a need for organizations to incorporate this strategy in the workplace to adhere to principles of inclusivity.

This is presented in Figure 4 below.

Figure 4: Strategies to improve inclusivity in the workplace

5. Conclusion and Recommendations

From the research, the respondents are aware of the importance of diversity and inclusion in the workplace at 84%. They are also aware that if diversity and inclusion were emphasized in the workplace there would be fewer

conflicts (92%), improved customer service (75%), increased creativity and innovation (92%), and improved employee morale and productivity (88%) and creation of promotion opportunities at 80%.

The respondents also felt that obstacles to diversity and inclusion were discrimination (94%), lack of diverse recruitment (98%), limited resources (97%), leadership commitment (93%) and lack of training (91%).

The respondents also rated the strategies to improve inclusivity as employee resource groups at 97%, inclusive training and development at 80%, leadership commitment at 88%, and open communication at 86%.

From this research and the literature reviewed in this article, these are the benefits of diversity and inclusion in the workplace.

- Better problem solving
- More creativity and Innovation
- Better understanding of customers
- Aids in recruiting and preserving top talent
- Brings a positive workplace culture

The challenges of incorporating diversity and inclusion in the workplace include

- Unconscious biases
- Lack of diversity at the top
- Resistance to change
- Lack of accountability
- Lack of inclusive leadership
- Inadequate resources
- Limited commitment from top management

These are the recommendations that should be incorporated for an organization to achieve diversity and inclusion in

the workplace:

- Establishment of employee resource groups
- Incorporate diverse recruitment every time there is a recruitment
- Leadership commitment.
- Inclusive training and development
- Open communication and teamwork
- Monitoring and evaluation.
- Allocate resources for this noble cause.
- Programs that help employees in managing work-life balance
- Transparent policies and practices

In conclusion, an inclusive workplace promotes a sense of belonging and inspires employee performance. Let every organization endeavor to incorporate diversity and inclusion in the workplace and thereby reap the benefits.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

1. Harwood, J. (2020) 'Social identity theory', *The International Encyclopedia of Media Psychology*, pp. 1-7.
2. Jejenywa, Temitayo Oluwaseun, Mhlongo, N.Z. and Jejenywa, Titilola Olaide (2024) 'Diversity and inclusion in the workplace: a conceptual framework comparing the USA and Nigeria', *International Journal of Management & Entrepreneurship Research*, 6(5), pp. 1368-1394.
3. Kinyanjui, S. (2013) 'Innovative strategies for managing workforce diversity in Kenyan leading corporations in present global scenario', *International Journal of Business and Management*, 8(15), p. 20.
4. Kiradoo, G. (2022) 'Diversity, equity, and inclusion in the workplace: strategies for achieving and sustaining a diverse workforce', *Advance Research in Social Science and Management*, Edition, 1, pp. 139-151.
5. KS, U.M. et al. (2024) 'Diversity And Inclusion In The Workplace: Best Practices For HR Professionals', *Educational Administration: Theory and Practice*, 30(6), pp. 2146-2153.
6. Kyomugisha, A. (2016) 'Effect of workforce diversity management on the performance of international development non-governmental organizations in Kenya'.
7. Ma, A.C. and Rast, D.E. (2017) 'Optimal distinctiveness theory', *Encyclopedia of personality and individual differences*, pp. 1-8.
8. Morfaki, C. and Morfaki, A. (2022) 'Managing workforce diversity and inclusion: a critical review and future directions', *International Journal of Organizational Leadership*, 11(4), pp. 426-443.
9. Mukuma Kyambi, J. (2015) 'Influence of Human Resource Diversity Management Practices on Performance of Non-Commercial Government Agencies in Kenya'.
10. Ngura, J. and Gichana, J.O. (no date) 'WORKFORCE DIVERSITY MANAGEMENT PRACTICES AND EMPLOYEE PERFORMANCE AMONG SELECTED CIVIL SOCIETY ORGANIZATIONS IN KENYA'.

